

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D1.5 COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITY REPORT

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP 1
Task	Task 1.1
Due date	30 September 2021
Submission date	29 October 2021
Deliverable lead	VRT
Version	1.0
Authors	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT)
Reviewers	Heikki Haldre (Exit Academy)

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

Abstract	This deliverable provides an overview of the community building activities the STADIEM consortium organized or participated in during year 1 of the project. It relates to D1.1 (Community Building Strategy) and D1.2 (Community Map and Database). As such, it gives an overview of the community building activities for each group of stakeholders identified according to their level of engagement: 1) Inform, 2) Convince, 3) Engage.
Keywords	Community building strategy, community management, community engagement, community building activities, stakeholders

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
V0.1	From 03/09 to 20/10/2021	Collection of input	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT) Einar Kaslegard & Marianne Fjellhaug (MCB) Dr. Tanja Deuerling (NMA) Sten Saluveer (Storytek) Lina Silveira (F6S) Galileo Disperati (Martel Innovate) Carmela Asero (EBU)
V0.2	22/10/2021	First full draft ready for internal review	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT)
V0.3	29/10/2021	Internal review	Heikki Haldre (Exit Academy)
V0.4	29/10/2021	Addressing internal review	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT)
V1.0	29/10/2021	Final version ready for submission to EC	Dr. Anneke Geyzen (VRT)

DISCLAIMER

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the "Startup Driven Innovation in European Media" (STADIEM) project's consortium under EC grant agreement 957321 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© 2020 - 2023 STADIEM Consortium

Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:		R
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides an overview of the community building activities the STADIEM consortium has organized or participated in during year 1 of the project. It relates to D1.1 (Community building strategy) and D1.2 (Community Map and Database). As such, it provides an overview of the community building activities per group of stakeholders identified according to their level of engagement:

- ➔ Inform: stakeholders we wish to inform about STADIEM, but we do not expect them to play an active role.
 - Cultural/artistic organisations
 - Sectors/verticals that are not related to the media industry
 - Standardisation bodies / initiatives
 - Users / audience / civil society
 - Public authorities / regulators / policy makers
- ➔ Convince: stakeholders we aim to convince to follow STADIEM, albeit from a distance.
 - Non-media sectors / verticals that are related, for example because they use crossroad technology
 - Media producers, traditional media, operators
 - Researchers in industry and academia / education
- ➔ Engage: stakeholders we aim to strongly involve. We expect them to participate actively in the community and we would like for them to take on an ambassador role as well.
 - Tech innovators
 - Incubators and accelerators
 - Investors
 - Corporates
 - Start-ups, scale-ups and SMEs (in media tech)

The completed activities show that most KPIs have been met and even exceeded for year 1 and open call 1. COVID-19 containment measures did impact participation in/organization of physical events, but the STADIEM partners have instead focused on digital events where possible. STADIEM is most impactful on the convince and engage segment of stakeholders.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 1 INTRODUCTION7
- 2 INFORM9
- 3 CONVINCED.....11
- 4 ENGAGE13
- 5 CONCLUSIONS16

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE INFORM STAKEHOLDER GROUP 9

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE CONVINC STAKEHOLDER GROUP 11

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE ENGAGE STAKEHOLDER GROUP 13

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This deliverable provides an overview of the community building activities the STADIEM consortium has organized or participated in during year 1 of the project. It relates to D1.1 (Community building strategy) and D1.2 (Community Map and Database). It will distinguish between activities we set up ourselves and activities organized by third parties. It will also indicate which consortium partners were involved in what activity.

1.2 TARGET GROUPS OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

We divided the stakeholder ecosystem into three main groups, in order to structure our community building strategy and to keep the community building activities manageable.

- **Inform** – This first group of stakeholders needs to be informed and updated about the project and its outcomes. The level of engagement is limited to raising awareness and sharing information, which will be addressed via our communication strategy. To be informed stakeholders are:
 - Cultural/artistic organisations
 - Sectors/verticals that are not related to the media industry
 - Standardisation bodies / initiatives
 - Users / audience / civil society
 - Public authorities / regulators / policy makers
- **Convince** - The second group of stakeholders is the group we aim to convince. These are stakeholders that need to be persuaded about the value of the project, as we count on their timely contributions. To be convinced stakeholders are:
 - Non-media sectors / verticals that are related, for example because they use crossroad technology
 - Media producers, traditional media, operators
 - Researchers in industry and academia / education
- **Engage** - The third group are the stakeholders we want to strongly involve. These are considered to be the (future) active members of our community and are expected to actively participate in the community. In addition to directly contributing to the project, stakeholders engaged in the project can also act as ambassadors. As such, they are able to leverage their own networks and amplify the impact of the STADIEM project. To be engaged stakeholders are:
 - Tech innovators
 - Incubators and accelerators
 - Investors
 - Corporates
 - Start-ups, scale-ups and SMEs (in media tech)

A detailed overview of these stakeholders can be found in D1.2 (Community map).

1.3 IMPACT OF COVID-19 RESTRICTION MEASURES

Tables 1, 2 and 3 work with a colour code, to highlight where we stand in light of the set KPIs:

KPIs met or exceeded
Slightly underperforming
KPIs not met because of COVID

1.4 IMPACT OF COVID-19 RESTRICTION MEASURES

The STADIEM project kicked off in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic, leaving the STADIEM consortium no choice but to pivot and launch the project digitally. This particular and unforeseeable turn of events has also impacted the community building strategy and activities.

Up until now, the activities have mostly taken place remotely, following national and European COVID-19 containment measures. This means that for KPIs related to physical events, STADIEM is currently underperforming because either events were canceled or COVID-19 travel restrictions prevented participation. However, STADIEM looked for digital alternatives and is right on track and even exceeds the KPIs for digital activities and events linked to the different phases of the programme. Moreover, STADIEM is also taking advantage of the release of (some of) the COVID-19 containment measures in Europe to participate in real-life events, such as Future Week (27 September – 1 October 2021), IBC (3-6 December 2021) and SLUSH (1-2 December 2021).

2 INFORM

This section gives an overview of the planned community building activities for the INFORM group of stakeholders, the actual activities and the partners' participation.

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE INFORM STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder group	Planned activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/KPIs	Partners involved
INFORM	STADIEM website	>1.500 unique visitors per month	>1.500 since the website's inception	Martel
	STADIEM promotional videos	4 videos per year + 100 views per video	6 videos on YouTube + 523 total views	Martel
	Communication on social media, such as LinkedIn and Twitter	Twitter > 300 followers LinkedIn > 100 followers	>300.000 impressions on Twitter and LinkedIn combined 166 followers on Twitter 274 followers on LinkedIn The results of our social media campaigns are above expectations. The number of followers for Twitter and LinkedIn combined has exceeded the set KPIs	Martel
	Word-to-mouth campaigns during industry-networking events	Not applicable	Word-to-mouth campaigns to the following stakeholders: government ecosystem partners (Start-Up Estonia and Accelerate Estonia) and government administrations (Estonian Ministry of Culture), investors and portfolio managers (i.e. investment funds), ecosystem organizations and expert service providers, and start-ups as OC1	Storytek

			and OC2 beneficiaries. These campaigns were both one-to-one meetings and start-up/ecosystem events, such as Artic15, Latitude59, Collision, Start-up Day	
--	--	--	--	--

3 CONVINC

This section gives an overview of the planned community building activities for the CONVINC group of stakeholders, the actual activities and the partners' participation.

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE CONVINC STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder group	Planned activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/KPIs	Partners involved
CONVINCE	Invitations to participate in workshops/events	At least 6 per year	<p>Future Media Hubs on 12 March, 9 July and 10 September 2021</p> <p>3 FMH invitations in year 1 and slightly underperforming vis-à-vis the set KPI. However, now that we have completed the Match phase and are running the Develop phase, STADIEM is gaining momentum in the ecosystem which, in turn, might result in more invitations.</p> <p>Additionally, COVID-19 containment measures no doubt explain the slight underperformance in this section. A lot of events got canceled, meaning that invitations have been sparse.</p>	VRT
	Engage at workshops/events	At least 6 per year	<p>Artic15, Infrachain Summit, FDCP Summit, B3 Biennale, EFFT Tallinn, Artech 2021, GDM 2021, NMA Demo Day on 12 October 2021</p> <p>8 during year 1 and thus exceeding the set KPI</p>	Storytek NMA

	<p>Targeted publications</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>4 press releases distributed to 30 specialized publications in 13 different European countries</p> <p>Article on STADIEM in the Q4/2021 issue of Tech-I magazine</p> <p>Several partners have sent out dedicated newsletters in which they highlighted STADIEM</p>	<p>Martel EBU VRT MCB NMA</p>
--	------------------------------	-----------------------	---	---

4 ENGAGE

This section gives an overview of the planned community building activities for the CONVINCe group of stakeholders, the actual activities and the partners' participation.

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE ENGAGE STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder group	Planned activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/KPIs	Partners involved
ENGAGE	Webinars to promote the programme	2 per open call	2 webinars for open call 1 (February + March 2021)	Martel VRT MCB F6S
	Showcasing and getting together at international events facilitated by the STADIEM network	Not applicable	During year 1 of the project, we were not able to attend many events due to the COVID-19 containment measures. However, the STADIEM consortium is committed to participating in several events organized in year 2, such as Infrachain, EFFT, SLUSH and IBC	All partners
	Showcasing and getting together at international events organized by the STADIEM network	Not applicable	During year 1 of the project, we were not able to attend many events due to the COVID-19 containment measures. However, we organized a few digital events and we have also engaged in organizing a real-life event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Virtual Media Match Day, 20 May 2021 (NMA) - Latitude59, 27-28 May 2021 (Storytek) - Mediatech on stage, 22 June 2021 (VRT & MCB) 	VRT MCB NMA Storytek EBU

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marché du Film, 6-15 July 2021 (Storytek) - Start-Up Day Estonia, 25-27 August 2021 (Storytek) - Future Week in Bergen, 27 September – 1 October 2021 (MCB) - NMA Demo Day, 12 October 2021 (NMA) 	
	Big Bang proceeding the Match phase of OC1	1 event	Big Bang event held on 19 May 2021 for the 40 selected start-ups of OC1	NMA VRT MCB Storytek
	Develop Phase Onboarding OC1	Not applicable	Onboarding event organized on 30 August 2021v for the 16 selected start-ups for the Develop Phase of OC1. The programme included an overview of the Develop expectations, as well as a community building event	VRT MCB NMA Storytek
	Participation in project-related events	At least 4	Pitching events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Media corporates, 1-15-22-29 June 2021 - Future Media Hubs, 5 July 2021 - Sports, 9 July 2021 - RTL, 11 July 2021 - Future Peak, 11-18-25 June & 2 July 2021 	VRT MCB NMA Storytek

			<p>Events for high-level stakeholder engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sander Saar - Guido Van Nispen <p>With 7 events during year 1, we have exceeded the set KPI</p>	
	Demo Day at the end of the project	1 Demo Day per open call	We have decided to already organize a Demo Day at the end of the Develop phase in February 2022, to showcase the media solutions the selected start-ups and scale-ups have worked on.	All partners
	Access to and integration in the partners' hubs and networks	Not applicable	All partners confirm that STADIEM and the selected start-ups and scale-ups have been given access to and integrated in their respective hubs and networks	All partners
	Videos, interview and success stories online	Not applicable	<p>1 news article on the Match phase start-ups' takeaways, published on the website and promote on STADIEM's social media channels in August 2021</p> <p>2press releases highlighting the VRT use cases in the Develop phase, September 2021</p> <p>Other highlights of STADIEM and the selected start-ups and scale-ups on social media channels and in newsletters</p>	Martel VRT MCB NMA

5 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presented an overview of the completed community building activities per identified group of stakeholders for year 1 of the project.

The completed activities show that most KPIs have been met and even exceeded for year 1 and open call 1. COVID-19 containment measures did impact participation in/organization of physical events, but the STADIEM partners have instead focused on digital events where possible. STADIEM is most impactful on the convince and engage segment of stakeholders.

Moreover, they have already highlighted several physical events in the upcoming months where STADIEM and its selected start-ups and scale-ups will be showcased (IBC, Slush).

